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Parental Involvement and Barriers Towards Grade 1 Learners' Academic Achievement

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Abstract

This study assessed the parental involvement and barriers of the parents of Grade 1 learners towards academic achievement of the learners in Guadalupe Elementary School for the school year 2022-2023, as basis for the crafting of intervention plan. The study utilized a descriptive -correlational method of research using the questionnaire as the main data-gathering tool and provide a valuable snapshot of parental involvement and barriers related to academic achievement. The findings revealed that parent's involvement as describe in the following indicators Type 1 Parenting, Type 2 Communicating, Type 3 Volunteering, Type 5 Decision- Making, Type 6 Collaborating Community has verbal interpretation Strongly Agree, while only Type 4 Learning at Home was interpreted as Slightly Agree. As to the levels of the different types of barriers on parental involvement, it was revealed that Time Constraints, Communication Barriers, Lack of Resources were interpreted as Strongly Agree while School Environment was interpreted as Slightly Agree. There was no significant relationship between the profile variables, barriers and the academic achievement among grade 1 learners since while there was a significant relationship between the academic achievement and the extent of parental involvement of the parents of Grade 1 learners since the p-values is 0.03 which is less that the level of significance. This concludes that the extent of parental involvement plays an important aspect on children's academic achievements specially in achieving learning in the classroom. Parents who always extend their support and provide a strong foundation that help improve the academic performance of the learners.

Keywords: *parental involvement and barriers, academic achievement, descriptive-correlational, grade 1 learners*

Introduction

Family in the Philippines is perceived as an important part of the society. It has been shaped by the unique history, values, experiences, adaptations, and ways of being that characterize the Filipino people and their culture (Adams, 2015). Coupled with the long history of political and social strife, Filipino parents face insurmountable challenges in raising their children (Blair, 2014).

Parental involvement is widely recognized as a significant factor influencing a child's educational journey. Numerous studies have shown that when parents actively engage in their children's education, learners tend to perform better academically, have higher attendance rates, improved behavior, and enhanced self-esteem. Parental involvement can take various forms, including participating in school activities, assisting with homework, attending parent-teacher conferences, and fostering a conducive learning environment at home. However, the nature and extent of parental involvement can vary based on cultural, socioeconomic, and individual differences.

While parental involvement is known to yield positive outcomes, there are often barriers that hinder effective collaboration between parents and schools. These barriers can be multifaceted and may include factors such as parents' lack of time due to work commitments, limited understanding of their role in education, language barriers, cultural differences, and socioeconomic challenges. Exploring these barriers is vital for devising strategies that can bridge the gap between schools and parents, ultimately fostering an environment conducive to enhanced academic achievement.

In this regard, Hoover-Dempsey et al. (2015) acknowledged that parental involvement is a vital issue in the educational process and therefore requires school to engage and collaborate with parents to improve school success. It is not about parent involvement as such, but about parents who are not involved yet, or who are not involved in the right way, but can get really well-involved if they accommodate invitations from school.

Grade 1 is a pivotal juncture in a child's academic progression. It marks the initiation of formal schooling and lays the foundation for subsequent years of learning. During this phase, parental involvement can significantly impact a child's perception of school, attitudes towards learning, and overall academic performance. Thus, understanding the dynamics of parental involvement in Grade 1 becomes imperative for educators, parents, and policymakers to enhance the educational experience for young learners.

The findings of this research have the potential to impact various stakeholders in the education system. For educators, understanding the relationship between parental involvement and Grade 1 learners' academic achievement can inform instructional approaches, curriculum design, and strategies for involving parents in the learning process. Schools can implement targeted interventions to overcome the identified barriers and create more inclusive and collaborative educational environments. Policymakers can use the research insights to develop policies that promote and support parental involvement in early education.

In essence, this aims to contribute to the growing body of knowledge on the pivotal role of parental involvement in Grade 1 learners' academic achievement. By exploring both the positive impacts and barriers associated with parental involvement, educators, parents, and policymakers can collaboratively work towards ensuring that Grade 1 learners receive the necessary support to thrive academically,

setting them on a trajectory of success throughout their educational journey.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 gender;
 - 1.3 highest educational attainment;
 - 1.4 marital status; and
 - 1.5 combined monthly family income?
2. To what extent of parents' involvement as described in the following indicators:
 - 2.1 type 1 parenting;
 - 2.2 type 2 communicating;
 - 2.3 type 3 volunteering;
 - 2.4 type 4 learning at home;
 - 2.5 type 5 decision- making; and
 - 2.6 type 6 collaborating community?
3. What are levels of the different types of barriers on parental involvement as described in the following:
 - 3.1 time constraints;
 - 3.2 communication barriers;
 - 3.3 lack of resources; and
 - 3.4 school environment?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the demographic profile and the extent of the involvement of the parents and barriers to their children?

Methodology

This research study utilized a descriptive-correlational method of research using the questionnaire as the main data-gathering tool.

The researcher utilized an adapted questionnaire from Rahman (2001) The Effects of Parent Involvement on Student Success. The questionnaire comprises three (3) parts. Part 1, demographic profile. Part 2, the extent of parents' involvement. And part 3, the levels of the different types of barriers on parental involvement.

A descriptive-correlational research method in this context can provide a valuable snapshot of parental involvement and barriers related to academic achievement. It lays the groundwork for further in- depth studies or interventions aimed at addressing these issues.

To describe the nature of parental involvement in their children's education and categorize common barriers parents face in becoming involved in their children's education, the researchers conduct an interview with the 30 Grade 1 parents of Guadalupe Elementary School. 10 are male and 20 are female. The respondents were given questionnaires to be answered.

In addition, weighted mean, percentage and Pearson r correlation were used in analyzing the gathered data.

Results and Discussion

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 1. Profile of the Parents N=30

Age	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
26-30	8	26.67
31-35	8	26.67
36-40	9	30.00
41-45	3	10.00
46 and above	2	6.66
Total	30	100
Gender	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Male	10	33.33
Female	20	66.67
Total	30	100

<i>Marital Status</i>	<i>Frequency (f)</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Single	2	6.67
Married	17	56.66
Remarried	9	30.00
Guardian	2	6.67
Total	30	100
<i>Highest Educational Attainment</i>	<i>Frequency (f)</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Elementary Graduate	7	23.33
High School Level	2	6.67
High School Graduate	17	56.66
Vocational	2	6.67
College Level	2	6.67
Total	30	100
<i>Combined Family Monthly Income</i>	<i>Frequency (f)</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Less than 5,000.00	9	30.00
5,001.00- 10,000.00	16	53.33
10,001.00 and above	5	16.67
Total	30	100

As shown in the table on the demographic profile of the respondents, it was revealed that majority or 9 out of 30 respondents were at the age between 36-40 years old or with a percentage of 30%. There are 8 out of 30 or 26.67% belongs to 26 to 35 years old, 3 out of 30 or 10% are at the age bracket 41-45 years old and 2 out of 30 or 6.66% belong to 46 years old and above. This implies that majority of the respondents are at the age 36-40 years old.

As to their gender, there are 10 out of 30 or 33.33% male while 20 out of 30 or 66.67% female. This implies that female parents of the Grade 1 learners outnumbered male parents.

As to the marital status, it was found out that 17 out of 30 or 56.66% are married, 9 out of 30 or 30% are remarried and 2 out of 30 or 6.67% are single and guardian respectively. This implies that majority of the parents of the learners of Grade 1 in Guadalupe are married.

As to their highest educational attainment, it was revealed that 17 out of 30 or 56.66% are high school graduate, 7 out of 30 or 23.33% are elementary graduate while 2 out of 30 or 6.67% are high school level, vocational and college level respectively.

As to their combine monthly income, it surfaced that there are 16 out of 30 or 53.33% have monthly combined income of 5,001-10,000.00, there are 9 out of 30 or 30% have monthly combined income of 5,000.00 below and there are 5 out of 30 or 16.67% have monthly combined income 10,001.00 and above. This would simply imply that majority of the respondents have earned for living and for the support of their family.

Student's Academic Achievement of Grade 1 Learners

Table 2. Student's Grade Point Average

<i>Grading Point Average</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>VI</i>
90-100	16	Outstanding
85-89	9	Very Satisfactory
80-84	5	Satisfactory
75-79	0	Fairly Satisfactory
Below 75	0	Did Not Meet Expectation
N=30		

Table 2 shows the Grade 1 learners Grade Point Average (GPA). The highest frequency of students falls within the "Outstanding" category (90-100 GPA), with 16 students achieving this level. This suggests a significant portion of learners performing exceptionally well academically. Following this, 9 students fall within the "Very Satisfactory" category (85-89 GPA), indicating a substantial number of learners performing at a high level. Only 5 students fall within the "Satisfactory" category (80-84 GPA), indicating a smaller proportion of students achieving at this level. Interestingly, there are no students in the "Fairly Satisfactory" category (75-79 GPA) or below, suggesting that no students fall below the satisfactory level.

The data underscores the importance of parental involvement in students' academic success. This demonstrates that parental involvement positively impacts academic achievement across all grade levels (Fan & Chen, 2001). This involvement can take various forms, including monitoring homework, attending parent-teacher conferences, and engaging in educational activities at home.

Extent of Parental Involvement

Table 3. *Parents Involvement in terms of Type 1 Parenting*

Type 1 Parenting	VM	VI
I am actively involved in creating a supportive home environment for my child's learning.	4.21	Strongly Agree
Eating meals together is important.	4.45	Strongly Agree
Average Weighted Mean	4.33	Strongly Agree

Legend: 4.21- 5.00 Strongly Agree; 3.21- 4.20 Slightly Agree; 2.61-.3.40 Undecided; 1.81- 2.60 Slightly Agree; 1.00- 1.80 Strongly Disagree

As shown in the table 3, the average weighted mean on parents' involvement in terms of type 1 which is parenting garnered 4.33 with a verbal interpretation Strongly Agree. This means that the actively participation of the parents play a huge and important role in enhancing academic achievements of their children. It was noticed that if parents and children eat their meals together can increase the motivation of their children in school.

Table 4. *Parents Involvement in terms of Type 2 Communicating*

Type 2 Communicating	WM	VI
Communicating with my child's teacher is a pleasant experience.	4.29	Strongly Agree
Monitoring my child's homework is an important part of his/her education.	4.42	Strongly Agree
Average Weighted Mean	4.36	Strongly Agree

Legend: 4.21- 5.00 Strongly Agree; 3.21- 4.20 Slightly Agree; 2.61-.3.40 Undecided; 1.81- 2.60 Slightly Agree; 1.00- 1.80 Strongly Disagree

As reflected in table 4 on parents' involvement in terms of type 2 communicating, the average weighted mean is 4.27 which interpreted as Strongly Agree. This means that monitoring and constant communication of the parents with their children play a significant impact for the improvement of the academic achievements in school. It is very crucial on the part of the parents to have constants touch with all the school activities so that they would know how their children behave in school.

Table 5. *Parents Involvement in terms of Type 3 Volunteering*

Type 3 Volunteering	WM	VI
Parents should not be asked to volunteer at school.	4.18	Strongly Agree
I attend parent/teacher conferences	4.36	Strongly Agree
Average Weighted Mean	4.27	Strongly Agree

Legend: 4.21- 5.00 Strongly Agree; 3.21- 4.20 Slightly Agree; 2.61-.3.40 Undecided; 1.81- 2.60 Slightly Agree; 1.00- 1.80 Strongly Disagree

As shown in the table 5, the role of the parents to their children according to type 3 which is volunteering has an average weighted mean of 4.27 which is interpreted as Strongly Agree. This means that the presence of the parents in school such as attending homeroom parent teacher meeting can influence on the learner's academic achievement. A parent-teacher conference is a great opportunity to discuss and deliberate the child's progress.

Table 6. *Parents Involvement in terms of Type 4 Learning at Home*

Type 4 Learning at Home	WM	VI
Helping my child with homework is important.	4.42	Strongly Agree
I have difficulty helping my child with homework.	3.36	Slightly Agree
Average Weighted Mean	3.89	Slightly Agree

Legend: 4.21- 5.00 Strongly Agree; 3.21- 4.20 Slightly Agree; 2.61-.3.40 Undecided; 1.81- 2.60 Slightly Agree; 1.00- 1.80 Strongly Disagree

As surfaced in the table 6 on parents' involvement in terms of type 4 learning at home, the average weighted mean is 3.89 which has verbal interpretation as Strongly Agree. This indicates that parents should help their children in doing homework. It also helps them develop a sense of responsibility, pride in a job well done, and a work ethic that will benefit them well beyond the classroom. Parents can give kids lots of homework help, primarily by doing homework a priority and helping them develop good study habits.

Table 7. *Parents Involvement in terms of Type 5 Decision- Making*

Type 5 Decision- Making	WM	VI
It's important to be active and to participate in school organizations, i.e. PTA, booster club, etc. with regards to decision- making.	4.32	Strongly Agree
Academic decisions are open to feedback and adaptation for continuous improvement.	4.46	Strongly Agree
Average Weighted Mean	4.39	Strongly Agree

Legend: 4.21- 5.00 Strongly Agree; 3.21- 4.20 Slightly Agree; 2.61-.3.40 Undecided; 1.81- 2.60 Slightly Agree; 1.00- 1.80 Strongly Disagree

As reflected in table 7 on Parents Involvement in terms of Type 5 Decision- Making, the average weighted mean is 4.39 with verbal interpretation of Strongly Agree. This means that parents' involvement in decision making is important because parents know their child best. The input of the parents is instrumental in making sure that the student receives appropriate support, and that necessary changes are made learners can be fully included in the classroom and school achievements.

Table 8. *Parents Involvement in terms of Type 6 Collaborating Community*

<i>Type 6 Collaborating Community</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>
Collaborative efforts between schools and the community positively impact academic achievement.	4.54	Strongly Agree
Community resources and partnerships contribute to improved educational opportunities for students.	4.43	Strongly Agree
Average Weighted Mean	4.49	Strongly Agree

4.21- 5.00 Strongly Agree; 3.21- 4.20 Slightly Agree; 2.61-.3.40 Undecided; 1.81- 2.60 Slightly Agree; 1.00- 1.80 Strongly Disagree

As shown in the table 8, it was revealed that the average weighted mean of 4.49 which is interpreted as Strongly Agree. This means that collaborative efforts between schools and the community positively impact academic achievement. Community Schools Partnerships offer communities the opportunity to support the needs of children and families with an intentional, enhanced and supported in achieving academic success and best learning outcomes.

Different Types and Levels of Barriers of Parental Involvement

Table 9. *Different Types and Levels of Barriers of Parental Involvement*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>WM</i>	<i>VI</i>
Time Constraints:		
I find it challenging to be involved in my child's education due to time constraints, such as work or other commitments.	4.23	Strongly Agree
Communication Barriers:		
There are communication barriers that make it difficult for me to engage with my child's school or teachers (e.g., language barriers, lack of information).	4.67	Strongly Agree
Lack Of Resources:		
The cost of educational resources or extracurricular activities is a barrier to my involvement in my child's education.	4.21	Strongly Agree
School Environment:		
The school environment is not welcoming or inclusive, which hinders my participation.	3.85	Slightly Agree
Average Weighted Mean	4.24	Strongly Agree

Legend: 4.21- 5.00 Strongly Agree; 3.21- 4.20 Slightly Agree; 2.61-.3.40 Undecided; 1.81- 2.60 Slightly Agree; 1.00- 1.80 Strongly Disagree

As shown in the tables 9 on the different types and levels of barriers of parental involvement, it surfaced that communication barriers have the highest weighted mean of 4.67, followed by time constraints which has a weighted mean of 4.23, then followed by lack of resources which has a weighted mean of 4.21 and lastly the school environment with a weighted mean of 3.85. Among the variables only lack of resources has a verbal interpretation as Slightly Agree while all other variables are Strongly Agree. However, the overall weighted mean of different types and levels of barriers of parental involvement is 4.24 which is interpreted as Strongly Agree. This implies that all aforementioned barriers experienced by the parents of the grade 1 learners are the predictor of their roles as parents.

Significant Relationship Between the Demographic Profile and the Parental Involvement of Parents

Table 10. *Relationship Between the Demographic Profile and the Parental Involvement of Parents*

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>
Age	-0.007	0.006	-1.113	0.272
Gender	0.065	0.101	0.649	0.520
Marital Status	-0.039	0.045	-0.851	0.399
Highest Educational Attainment	-0.069	0.053	-1.296	0.201
Combined Family Monthly Income	0.000	0.000	0.935	0.355

Table 10 exposes that there is no significant relationship between the profile variables, barriers and the academic achievement among grade 1 learners since the p- values of the variables are higher than the alpha level ($p > \alpha = 0.05$). This is also validated by the p-values found in Table 10 wherein all figures are greater than the level of significance (0.05). These findings signify that the enumerated profile variables cannot be considered as determinants of the academic achievements of the learners. It was noticed that the computed p-values of the variables are higher than the level of significance which leads to the decision accept the null hypothesis, it is therefore, there no significant relationships between the demographic profile and the academic achievements among the learners. This implies that demographic profile is not considered predictor on parental involvements. Regardless of the years of teaching experiences, ages, gender, education background, marital status and combined monthly income.

The variables are tested at 0.05 level of significance to find out the significant difference between the extent of parental involvement and academic achievement. The result is presented in Table 11. As reflected in the table, the p-value with the indicator specified

revealed a value which is lesser the alpha level of significance at 0.05, causing the null hypothesis to be rejected. This means that there is a significant relationship between the academic achievement and the extent of parental involvement of the parents of Grade 1 learners. This implies that parents of the learners who always practice facilitates their children, with always manage their time effectively, always conducive learning environment, and always utilizes multimedia in answering the module have significant effect on the academic performance.

Table 11. *Relationship Between Extent Of Parental Involvement And Academic Achievement*

Variables	Extent of Parental Involvement		Decision	Interpretation
	p-value	r-value		
Academic Achievement	0.03	0.89	Reject H ₀	Significant

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it can be concluded that the extent of parental involvement plays an important aspect on children's academic achievements specially in achieving learning in the classroom. Parents who always extend their support and provide a strong foundation that help improve the academic performance of the learners. This is supported by the Attachment Theory of Bowlby and Ainsworth, (2019) which posits that attachment theory is focused on the relationships and bonds between people, particularly long-term relationships, including those between a parent and child and thus improves the academic performance of the children.

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher endorsed that: (1) school leaders may empower the parents by providing a systematic and operational parent involvement routine in school; (2) the school shall include parents in all school activities in order to maintain strong bonds with their children; (3) teachers, parents and other stakeholders may come up with a strategic plan on providing strong support with the children through mentoring and coaching; (4) Researchers may conduct parallel study with the following suggested titles: (4.1) An adjunct Study in Parent Coaching in all Subject Areas; (4.2) Parent Coaching Style vis a vis Academic Performance among Kindergarten Learners; and (4.3) Parental Taxonomy Skills in Coaching and Mentoring with the learners.

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